

Deducing the relationship between physical constants from the numerical values of physical constants

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Abstract: Other basic physical constants can be derived as long as the Speed of light, the value of the Elementary charge, and the value of one of the two Vacuum dielectric constant and Permeability of vacuum are known.

Key words:Physical constant, universal Gravitational constant formula.

Because of the epidemic, I was bored at home, and I found a "numerical equation", gravity constant = Planck constant / electron rest mass / Rydberg constant. Then I went on to deduce, and I found a self-consistent system of "numerical equations".

Numerically, the equation system is self-consistent, has no extra numbers, and does not conflict with other "standard" physical formulas. It's just that from the existing physical constant units, some equations are difficult to understand.

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{h}) &= (\mathbf{k}_B)(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{c}), (\mathbf{k}_B) = \frac{(\mu_0)}{(\mathbf{c})^2}, [\alpha_o] = \frac{(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{c})^2}{2}, (\mathbf{h}) = (\mathbf{m}_e)[\alpha_o](\mathbf{c})(\mathbf{a}_o), (\mathbf{m}_{\text{atom}})(\mathbf{c})^2(\mathbf{m}_e)(\mathbf{c})^2 = \\ & \frac{(\mu_0)(\mathbf{e}_o)}{(\mathbf{a}_o)(\mathbf{c})}, \frac{(\mathbf{a}_o)(\mathbf{c})}{(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mu_0)} = \frac{(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{c})^2}{4\pi}, (\mathbf{k}_{\text{Ideal gas}}) = \frac{4}{(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{c})^2}, \frac{(\mathbf{k}_{\text{vacuum}})}{(\mathbf{k}_{\text{Ideal gas}})} = \frac{(\mathbf{k}_B)[\alpha_o]}{(\mathbf{m}_e)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)}. \end{aligned}$$

I don't know whether this self-consistent "numerical equation" shows the essence of some physical phenomena, or whether it is just a numerical equation game. But if we add in the known $(\epsilon_0)(\mu_0)(\mathbf{c})^2 = 1$, $(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{a}_o) = \frac{[\alpha_o]}{4\pi}$, if we assume that the above equation is true, we will find that other basic physical constants can be derived as long as we know the Speed of light, the value of the Elementary charge, and one of the two Vacuum dielectric constant and Permeability of vacuum.

And for the universal gravitation constant formula and the electrostatic constant formula,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{E}_m) &= \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)(\mathbf{c})^2(\mathbf{e}_o)^2}{4(\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)[\alpha_o](\mathbf{e}_o)}{2(\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)[\alpha_o](\mathbf{c})2\pi(\mathbf{e}_o)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{c})(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)[\alpha_o](\mathbf{c})2\pi(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{a}_o)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)}{(\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{c})[\alpha_o](\mathbf{r})^2}, \\ (\mathbf{E}_m) &= \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)(\mathbf{m}_e)[\alpha_o](\mathbf{c})2\pi(\mathbf{a}_o)}{(\mathbf{m}_e)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)(\mathbf{m}_{\text{atom}})(\mathbf{c})^4(\mathbf{a}_o)}{(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)(\mathbf{h})}{(\mathbf{m}_e)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_m)(\mathbf{G}_N)}{(\mathbf{r})^2}, \\ (\mathbf{E}_e) &= \frac{(\mathbf{q}_e)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_e)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{a}_o)}{[\alpha_o](\epsilon_0)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_e)(\mathbf{c})(\mathbf{a}_o)}{(\mathbf{e}_o)(\mathbf{R}_\infty)(\mathbf{r})^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{q}_e)(\mathbf{k})}{(\mathbf{r})^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Then I tried to restore the above "numerical equation" inference formula and hypothetically analyze why there is a discrepancy between the values of one of the above formulas.

Starting with the simplest reduced Planck constant, the equivalent formula of reduced Planck constant can be directly derived by using the definition formula of fine structure constant and the definition formula of centripetal force of electrons in circumferential motion provided by Coulomb gravity.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha_0] = \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)(\hbar)}, \\ \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)^2} = \frac{(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(a_0)} \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\hbar) = (m_e)[\alpha_0](c)(a_0), \\ \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)[\alpha_0](c)} = (\hbar), \end{array} \right.$$

And I guessed the equivalent formula of the Planck constant. The first reason why I want to guess the Planck constant is that after discovering the equivalent formula of the reduced Planck constant, I think the Planck constant may also have an equivalent formula. The second reason is that the Planck constant is so abrupt in the blackbody radiation formula that it is incompatible with other physical constants around it, and then takes the Boltzmann constant as the benchmark. Combined with other physical constants, it is found that the value obtained by multiplying the Boltzmann constant with the basic charge and the speed of light is too close to the Planck constant, and putting this equivalence into the blackbody radiation formula can eliminate the Planck constant and make the blackbody radiation formula a little more concise.

And then in the process of this calculation, I found that the reduced Planck constant and Planck constant in the "standard" physical formula were replaced by an equivalent formula, no matter how it was calculated, it was only approximate one, and then I was thinking, if there is an undiscovered relationship between physical constants, will the calculation between them be only approximate one because of the theoretical error and experimental error of some formulas? I have obtained many approximate formulas between physical constants, and then found that there will be conflicts between some physical constants, and then we can only make a choice, retaining several formulas that can be self-consistent and approximate one between physical constants. Among these formulas, some are really approximately one, others are only approximate 0.987 and one max 0.987.

Approximate one, I can believe that this is the theoretical error and experimental error of some formulas, but 0.987 is really different. To this day, I can explain this problem, that is, the relativistic effect, $(0.987) = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right)$, because I find that 0.987 are related to $(c)^2$, but I can't explain it, $\left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right)$.

From the point of view of the "numerical equation", and the inverse operation, there can be the following equation ,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (k_B) = \frac{(\mu_0)}{(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \\ [\alpha_0] * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) = \frac{(e_0)(c)^2}{2}, \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (1.3803 * 10^{-23}) = \frac{(4\pi * 10^{-7})}{(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \\ [7.2923 * 10^{-3}] * (0.98725) = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2}{2}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{(e_o)(\mu_o)}{2(k_B)[\alpha_o]} = 1, \\ (e_o)(c)^2(k_B)(c)^2 = 2[\alpha_o](\mu_o), \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{(e_o)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_o)[\alpha_o](c)} = \frac{(k_B)(e_o)(c)}{2\pi}, \\ 2\pi(e_o)(c)^2(k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_o)(c)^2 = 4\pi[\alpha_o], \end{cases}$$

However, the "standard" physical constant $(k_B) = (1.3806 * 10^{-23})$, $[\alpha_o] = [7.2973 * 10^{-3}]$ shows that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is very small.

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (k_B) = \frac{(\mu_o)}{(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \\ (k_{Ideal\ gas}) = \frac{4}{(e_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (1.3803 * 10^{-23}) = \frac{(4\pi * 10^{-7})}{(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \\ (2.7426 * 10^2) = \frac{4}{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} 2\pi(k_{Ideal\ gas})(e_o)(c)^2(k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_o)(c)^2 = 8\pi, \\ 8\pi(k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_o)(c)^2 = 2\pi(k_{Ideal\ gas})(e_o)(c)^2, \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} [\alpha_o] * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) = \frac{(e_o)(c)^2}{2}, \\ (k_{Ideal\ gas}) = \frac{4}{(e_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} [7.2923 * 10^{-3}] * (0.98725) = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2}{2}, \\ (2.7426 * 10^2) = \frac{4}{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} 2\pi[\alpha_o](k_{Ideal\ gas}) = 4\pi, \\ 16\pi[\alpha_o] = 2\pi(k_{Ideal\ gas})(e_o)(c)^2(e_o)(c)^2, \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (k_B) = \frac{(\mu_o)}{(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \\ [\alpha_o] * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) = \frac{(e_o)(c)^2}{2}, \\ (k_{Ideal\ gas}) = \frac{4}{(e_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (1.3803 * 10^{-23}) = \frac{(4\pi * 10^{-7})}{(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725) , \\ [7.2923 * 10^{-3}] * (0.98725) = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2}{2} , \\ (2.7426 * 10^2) = \frac{4}{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 2\pi(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})[\alpha_0](k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_0)(c)^2 = 4\pi, \\ 4\pi(k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_0)(c)^2 = 2\pi(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})[\alpha_0] , \\ 16\pi[\alpha_0] = 2\pi(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})(e_0)(c)^2(e_0)(c)^2(k_B)(c)^2, \\ 16\pi[\alpha_0](k_B)(c)^2(\epsilon_0)(c)^2 = 2\pi(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})(e_0)(c)^2(e_0)(c)^2, \end{array} \right.$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(k_{\text{Ideal gas}}) = (2.7315 * 10^2)$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(a_0)(c)}{(R_\infty)(\mu_0)} = \frac{(e_0)(c)^2}{4\pi} , \\ (R_\infty)(a_0) = \frac{[\alpha_0]}{4\pi} , \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(5.2793 * 10^{-11})(2.9979 * 10^8)}{(1.0992 * 10^7)(4\pi * 10^{-7})} = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2}{4\pi} , \\ (1.0992 * 10^7)(5.2793 * 10^{-11}) = \frac{[7.2923 * 10^{-3}]}{4\pi} , \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (a_0)^2(c)^2 = \frac{(e_0)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)} * \frac{[\alpha_0](c)}{4\pi} , \\ \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)} = \frac{[\alpha_0](c)}{4\pi} , \end{array} \right. \Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)(c)} = 1, \\ \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)} = \frac{[\alpha_0](c)}{4\pi} , \end{array} \right.$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(a_0) = (5.2917 * 10^{-11})$, $(R_\infty) = (1.0973 * 10^7)$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (h) = (k_B)(e_0)(c) = \frac{(e_0)(\mu_0)}{(c)} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) , \\ (h) = \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)[\alpha_0](c)} , \\ (m_e) = \frac{(h)}{[\alpha_0](c)(a_0)} , \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (6.6282 * 10^{-34}) = (1.3803 * 10^{-23})(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8) = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(4\pi * 10^{-7})}{(2.9979 * 10^8)} * (0.98725) , \\ (1.0552 * 10^{-34}) = \frac{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})^2}{4\pi(8.8541 * 10^8)[7.2923 * 10^{-3}](2.9979 * 10^8)} , \\ (9.1429 * 10^{-31}) = \frac{(1.0552 * 10^{-34})}{[7.2923 * 10^{-3}](2.9979 * 10^8)(5.2793 * 10^{-11})} , \end{array} \right.$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(h) = (6.6260 * 10^{-34})$, $(\hbar) = (1.0545 * 10^{-34})$, $(m_e) = (9.1093 * 10^{-31})$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

$$\begin{cases} (k_{\text{Ideal gas}}) = \frac{4}{(e_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt[2]{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \\ (k_{\text{Vacuum}}) = \frac{(k_B)[\alpha_o]}{(m_e)(R_\infty)} * \frac{4}{(e_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt[2]{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (2.7426 * 10^2) = \frac{4}{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \\ (2.7461) = \frac{(1.3803 * 10^{-23})[7.2923 * 10^{-3}]}{(9.1429 * 10^{-31})(1.0992 * 10^7)} * \frac{4}{(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725), \end{cases}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} 2\pi(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})(k_{\text{Vacuum}})(e_o)(c)^2(e_o)(c)^2(m_e)(R_\infty) = 32\pi(k_B)[\alpha_o], \\ \frac{(k_{\text{Vacuum}})(m_e)(R_\infty)}{(h)} = \frac{(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})(k_B)[\alpha_o]}{(h)}, \end{cases}$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(k_{\text{Vacuum}}) = (2.72)$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

$$\begin{cases} (E_e) = \frac{(q_e)}{4\pi(\epsilon_o)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(k)}{(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(c)(a_o)}{(e_o)(R_\infty)(r)^2}, \\ (E_m) = \frac{(q_m)(G_N)}{(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)[\alpha_o](c)2\pi(e_o)}{4\pi(\epsilon_o)(c)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)(m_e)[\alpha_o](c)2\pi(a_o)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(r)^2}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} \frac{(R_\infty)(k)}{(a_o)(c)^2} = \frac{1}{(e_o)(c)}, \\ (m_{\text{atom}})(c)^2 = \frac{(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_o)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt[2]{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \\ (e_o) = (m_e)(R_\infty)(c)[\alpha_o]^2, \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{(e_o)(R_\infty)(k)}{(a_o)} = (c), \\ (m_{\text{atom}})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2 = \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_o)} * \left(\sqrt[2]{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right), \end{cases}$$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{cases} (e_o)(R_\infty)^2(k) = \frac{[\alpha_o](c)}{4\pi}, \\ (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(G_N) = \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_o](c)[\alpha_o]. \end{cases}$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (G_N) = \frac{(h)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)} , \\ (m_{\text{atom}})(c)^2 = \frac{(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)(c)^2} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) , \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (6.5953 * 10^{-11}) = \frac{(6.6282 * 10^{-34})}{(9.1429 * 10^{-31})(1.0992 * 10^7)} , \\ (1.6783 * 10^{-27})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2 = \frac{(1.0992 * 10^7)(6.5953 * 10^{-11})}{(5.2793 * 10^{-11})(2.9979 * 10^8)^2} * (0.98725) , \end{array} \right.$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(G_N) = (6.674 * 10^{-11})$, $(m_{\text{atom}}) = (1.6749 * 10^{-27})$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (K_J) = \frac{2(e_0)}{(h)} , \\ (\mu_B) = \frac{(e_0)(h)}{2(m_e)} , \\ (R) = (k_B)(N_A) , \end{array} \right. \Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (K_J) * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) = \frac{2(c)}{(\mu_0)} , \\ (\mu_B) = \frac{(a_0)[\alpha_0]^2}{(c)} * \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{(c)^2}{(2\pi)^2(c)^2}} \right) , \\ \frac{1}{2}(R) = \frac{(\mu_0)}{2\pi(e_0)(c) * (10)^3} , \end{array} \right.$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (4.8329 * 10^{14}) * (0.98725) = \frac{2(2.9979 * 10^8)}{(4\pi * 10^{-7})} , \\ (9.2451 * 10^{-24}) = \frac{(5.2793 * 10^{-11})[7.2923 * 10^{-3}]^2}{(2.9979 * 10^8)} * (0.98725) , \\ \frac{1}{2}(8.3282) = \frac{(4\pi * 10^{-7})}{2\pi(1.6021 * 10^{-19})(2.9979 * 10^8) * (10)^3} , \end{array} \right.$$

And the "standard" physical constant $(K_J) = (4.8359 * 10^{14})$, $(\mu_B) = (9.2740 * 10^{-24})$, $(R) = (8.3144)$, it can be seen that the numerical error between this "standard" physical constant and the physical constant obtained by the above equation is also very small.

If only the values of physical constants obtained by one or two formulas are similar to those of "standard" physical constants, it may be a coincidence, but the values of physical constants obtained by all the "numerical equations" above are similar to those of "standard" physical constants, and these "numerical equations" are self-consistent and can be converted into each other. This makes people wonder whether there is a unified theoretical system behind these equations.

Unfortunately, although I have deduced this, I am still very confused about what is behind these "digital equations". I hope there will be a journal to publish these things so that more people can see them and participate in them. To explain these things, if it is proved to be wrong, please deny it, and if it is proved to be correct, please propose a theoretical system that can justify itself.

Why is the ratio of Planck constant to reduced Planck constant 2π ? according to the above "numerical guess formula" and ignoring the relativistic effect,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(h)}{(\hbar)} = 2\pi, \\ \frac{(e_0)(\mu_0)}{(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)(a_0)} = 2\pi, \Rightarrow (e_0)(\mu_0)(R_\infty) = \frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0], \\ (R_\infty)(a_0) = \frac{[\alpha_0]}{4\pi}, \end{array} \right.$$

In the "standard" physical formula, the formula for calculating the ionization energy of hydrogen atom is $\frac{(h)(c)(R_\infty)}{(e_0)} = \frac{(13120000)(1000)(m_{atom})}{(e_0)} = 13.6 \text{ eV}$.

Then, according to the "numerical guess formula" above, there are $\frac{(h)(c)(R_\infty)}{(e_0)} = (\mu_0)(R_\infty) = (k_B)(c)^2(R_\infty) = \frac{\frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0]}{(e_0)} = 13.6 \text{ eV}$.

Then, $(E_m) = \frac{(q_m)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)2\pi(a_0)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)(h)}{(m_e)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_m)(G_N)}{(r)^2}$, $(E_e) = \frac{(q_e)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(c)(a_0)}{(e_0)(R_\infty)(r)^2} = \frac{(q_e)(k)}{(r)^2}$, so, $(m_e)(R_\infty)^2(c)(G_N) = \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{1}{2}(c)(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0]$.

So, does the ionization energy of other atoms also mean that the ionization energy is related to the Rydberg constant and permeability, or it can be converted by its electron orbital velocity?

Then, $(m_{atom})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2 = \frac{(\mu_0)(e_0)}{(a_0)(c)}$, so, $(m_e) = \frac{(\mu_0)(e_0)}{2\pi(a_0)(c)[\alpha_0](c)}$, $(m_{atom})(c)^4 = 2\pi[\alpha_0](c)$,
 $\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)[\alpha_0](c) = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)}$.

Therefore, for several equivalent formulas of the ionization energy of hydrogen atoms, there are $(h)(c)(R_\infty) = (e_0)(\mu_0)(R_\infty) = (e_0)(k_B)(c)^2(R_\infty) = (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(c)(G_N) = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^4(m_e)[\alpha_0](c)}{4\pi} = \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)} = \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2$.

$$(m_{atom})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2 = \frac{(\mu_0)(e_0)}{(a_0)(c)}, \frac{(e_0)^2(R_\infty)^2(\mu_0)(k)}{(c)(a_0)} = \frac{(e_0)[\alpha_0]}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)^2(a_0)}, \Leftrightarrow \frac{(e_0)(R_\infty)(k)}{(a_0)} = (c),$$

$$\frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = \frac{(h)}{(a_0)} = (m_{atom})(c)^2(m_e)(c)^2, \Leftrightarrow \frac{(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)(c)^2} = (m_{atom})(c)^2, \frac{(m_{atom})(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2(m_{atom})(c)^2}{(m_e)}$$

It can be seen that the physical constants can be inverted perfectly and there are no errors.

So, the question is, from the above equation, why is the electron escape velocity of the hydrogen atom equal to the encircling velocity, and there are some more constants in the gravitational formula and the electromagnetic formula? And why are atomic mass and electron mass treated differently in the gravitational formula?

So, can we assume that the scale of the basic atom is equivalent to the unit element of the definition domain of some mathematical formulas, and that the scale below the basic atom is beyond the scope of this definition domain?

Therefore, for the scale below the basic atom, some physical formulas are not applicable, and the derivation of the ionization energy of hydrogen atoms is, to

some extent, the operation of unit elements in the definition domain of physical formulas.

Where (ϵ_0) is the Vacuum dielectric constant, (μ_0) is the Permeability of vacuum, (c) is the Speed of light, (e_0) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (R_∞) is the Rydberg constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_{atom}) is the Basic atomic mass, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, $(\hbar)$ is the Reduced Planck constant, (h) is the Planck constant. (k_B) is the Boltzmann constant, (k) is the Electrostatic force constant, (G_N) is the Gravitational constant, $(k_{\text{Ideal gas}})$ is the Ideal gas temperature constant, (k_{Vacuum}) is the Vacuum background radiation temperature constant, (K_J) is the Josephson constant, (μ_B) is the Bohr magneton constant, (R) is the molar gas constant. Other physical constants can be deduced from these basic constants, so I won't write them.

Reference: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_physical_constants.